

Intensity correction factors for a cosmic ray neutron sensor

Darin Desilets
Hydroinnova LLC
Albuquerque, NM
darin@hydroinnova.com

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Abstract

This document describes algorithms for correcting neutron counting rates for geomagnetic latitude, altitude, solar activity and, when applicable, atmospheric humidity. Such factors apply to the real time processing of data from a Hydroinnova soil moisture stations and roving instruments.

Key words: scaling factors, CRNS, soil moisture

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1 Introduction

Hydroinnova's cosmic ray neutron sensors (CRNS) use ambient neutron intensity as a proxy for soil water content and snow water equivalent. A CRNS can be stationary, gathering time series at a discrete location, or roving, to enable mapping of soil moisture patterns in space and time. Both types of sensor entail corrections to the raw neutron data.

The basis of the technique is that any deviations from the baseline neutron counting rate is inversely proportional to the amount of soil moisture and/or snow water equivalent, the two variables of primary interest. However several other environmental variables can influence the baseline neutron intensity, and cause fluctuations in the raw counting rate, N . These unwanted fluctuations are eliminated by applying correction factors, resulting in a corrected counting rate N_{corr} .

This document describes key correction factors applied to raw data. This includes corrections for the spatial and temporal variability of neutron intensity. Spatial corrections are used in roving surveys, or to transfer the baseline counting rate (N_0) between fixed sites. The temporal corrections apply to correcting time series data. Of course, the spatial and temporal corrections are often related. For example, the barometric pressure correction and the elevation correction are essentially the same thing. In some circumstances spatial or temporal variations in some variables are small enough to be neglected. The user should apply his judgment in determining when and if the corrections are required.

The calculations described here are implemented as online utilities at <https://crnslab.org>, where additional materials, data and guides related to CRNS can be found.

Figure 1. CRNS station (model CRS2000/B) maintained by the University of Bristol.

2 Data processing algorithms

2.3 General framework

The corrected counting rate, N_{corr} , is calculated by multiplying the raw counting rate N by multiplying by a correction factor.

$$N_{\text{corr}} = N \cdot F(t) \quad (1)$$

The correction factor $F(t)$ can be decomposed into individual correction factors, each of which represent a different processes under consideration. For a mobile CRNS the main correction factors account for geomagnetic latitude (f_{lat}), barometric pressure (f_{bar}), solar activity (f_{sol}) and atmospheric humidity (f_{hum}). The total correction factor is then

$$F(t) = f_{\text{lat}} \cdot f_{\text{bar}} \cdot f_{\text{sol}} \cdot f_{\text{hum}} \quad (2)$$

Each correction factor serves to normalize the cosmic ray intensity to a set of reference conditions. These reference conditions can be arbitrarily chosen, so long as one is consistent. As reiterated below, f_{lat} and f_{bar} correct the baseline intensity to high latitude and sea level, respectively, f_{sol} normalizes to the conditions of 12 April 2018 UT, and f_{hum} normalizes the intensity to a dry atmosphere.

For a stationary probe, f_{lat} can be set to unity (which by definition makes the CRNS equivalent to the reference site). Furthermore, for an invasive snow measurement it is conventional to also set f_{hum} to 1, since the buried CRNS is not influenced by atmospheric humidity.

2.4 Cutoff rigidity

As charged particles (mostly protons) primary cosmic rays are deflected by Earth's magnetic field according to the right-hand rule. The horizontal component of the Earth's main dipole field is weaker toward the poles, which creates a pronounced latitude variation in cosmic ray intensity. Although the dipole component dominates the geomagnetic field, non-dipole components (most importantly the eccentric dipole but also other terms) can as well cause variations in intensity along longitude.

To calculate geomagnetic shielding for a given location, time and angle of incidence upon our atmosphere it is usually necessary to run numerical trajectory tracing simulation, particularly when dealing with higher order field components (Smart et al., 2000). These simulations determine the minimum magnetic rigidity (momentum to charge ratio) required for a cosmic ray to reach Earth's atmosphere.

The minimum (or "cutoff") rigidity for a location is closely related to the neutron intensity experienced at ground level. Above this minimum, some particles are allowed while others are rejected, until an upper cutoff is reached—beyond which all particles are allowed. The occurrence of this ambiguous region between the lower and upper cutoffs necessitates the use of effective cutoffs, as described by Smart et al. (2000).

As a measure of geomagnetic shielding we use the effective vertical cutoff rigidity (R_c) as defined by Smart et al. (2000). Cutoff rigidities are using the MAGNETOCOSMICS code (Desorgher, 2004) as implemented on <https://crnslab.org>. Further documentation on cutoff rigidities can be found here in Desilets (2021).

2.5 Atmospheric depth and barometric pressure

The mass thickness of atmosphere above a CRNS strongly influences neutron intensity. Barometric pressure, p , is usually a good proxy for atmospheric mass thickness (also called atmospheric depth). Pressure is typically recorded with an on-board pressure sensor. Atmospheric depth is directly proportional to pressure under conditions of low to modest wind speed¹. The conversion between pressure p [mb] and depth x [g cm⁻²] is

$$x = 10 p/g \quad (3)$$

where g is the local acceleration due to gravity in m s⁻². For most calculations one can assume $g = 9.80665$ m s⁻², which is the nominal value for sea level and mid latitude according to the ISO 80000 standard. Variations in gravity across Earth's surface can have some affect on shielding depth as calculated from a pressure sensor. This affect (typically small to begin with) can be reduced by an order of magnitude or more by applying simple geodetic corrections, such that local gravity is given by

$$g = g_{\text{SL}} + \delta g_{\text{H}} + \delta g_{\text{BC}} \quad (4)$$

where g_{SL} is the local gravity at sea level, which is modeled by the 1980 Geodetic Reference System formula (Moritz, 2000)

$$g_{\text{SL}} = 9.780327(1 + 0.0053024 \sin^2 \lambda - 0.0000058 \sin^2 2\lambda) \quad (5)$$

and δg_{H} is known as the free air correction (Heiskanen and Moritz, 1967), and can be approximated as

$$\delta g_{\text{H}} = 0.3086 \zeta \quad (6)$$

where ζ is the elevation above sea level in meters. Finally, δg_{BC} is the Bouguer correction (Hinze et al., 2005), calculated as

$$\delta g_{\text{BC}} = 4.193 \times 10^{-5} \rho_{\text{rck}} \zeta \quad (7)$$

where ρ_{rck} is the density of rock, taken to be 2670 kg m⁻³.

How much do these corrections matter? To find out let's consider what is probably the most extreme contrast in local gravity: the geographic poles versus the summit of Chimborazo, Ecuador ($\lambda=1^\circ$). The value of g at Chimbarozo is lower than at the poles by 0.65%. In this case the scaling factor between the two locations could be in error by as much as 5% if geodetic variations are not taken into account. By contrast within the contiguous US the difference in calculated intensity is only around 1% in what would likely be the most extreme comparison, from Blaine, WA to the summit of Emory Peak, TX. However, when considering non-contiguous Barrow, AK and Mauna Kea, HI, the maximum possible error in the US grows to 3%.

¹This correction becomes significant (> 1%) only when winds exceed 15 m s⁻¹. This level of wind is substantial, corresponding to a "near gale" on the Beaufort wind scale with "whole trees moving; resistance felt walking against wind"

2.6 Latitude correction

The latitude correction normalizes the intensity at any location to high geomagnetic latitude (effectively $R_C < 2$ GV). The correction factor at sea level is given by

$$f_{\text{lat}} = \frac{1}{1 - \exp(-\alpha R_C^k)} \quad (8)$$

where the denominator is the Dorman function (Dorman et al., 1970). I use the parameters $\alpha=9.694$ and $k=0.9954$ based on the 1996-97 sea level neutron monitor survey reported by Villoresi et al. (2000) representing solar minimum conditions. Although solar activity does influence the shape of the curve, this effect is fully accounted for by applying the solar correction described below. This works because the solar correction is latitude dependent, with larger corrections at higher geomagnetic latitudes. In consequence, only a single baseline latitude curve is needed in our algorithm in order to calculate neutron intensity anywhere, at any time.

2.7 Elevation/barometric correction

2.7.1 Barometric correction for fixed sites

A CRNS station can experience barometric pressure variations on the order of 10 mb. This has a significant influence on the N . The correction factor is a simple exponential relationship

$$f_{\text{bar}} = \exp[\beta(x-x_0)] \quad (9)$$

where x is atmospheric depth at the site at any given point in time, x_0 is a reference depth and β is the attenuation length at a point. The reference depth x_0 is generally assumed to be the approximate long term average value for the site. The exact choice of x_0 is unimportant so long as N_0 is defined for this same reference pressure.

The attenuation coefficient at a point is given by the following parameterization

$$\beta(R_C, x) = n[1 + \exp(-\alpha R_C^{-k})]^{-1} + \sum_{i=0}^q (b_{3i} + b_{3i+1}R_C + b_{3i+2}R_C^2) x^i \quad (10)$$

where $q=3$ and the coefficients are in Table 1.

The coefficients were found from a best fit of the results of Carmichael and Bercovitch (1969) supplemented by low-latitude surveys collected by the author and co-workers. This parameterization includes the effects of muons on total neutron production within the neutron monitor. Note that in some published works this affect is accounted for and removed; however for CRNS corrections it is desirable to include all sources of neutron production.

Based on comparisons with a “rock” neutron monitor used by the author and co-workers, the standard lead neutron monitor seems to accurately represent the same altitude dependence of neutron

intensity. This is fortunate given that the greatest wealth of spatiotemporal data is from standard neutron monitors.

Table 1. Parameters for calculating the barometric pressure coefficient.

n	1.231×10^{-02}
α	5.546×10^{-02}
k	6.012×10^{-01}
b_0	4.742×10^{-06}
b_1	-9.666×10^{-07}
b_2	1.428×10^{-09}
b_3	-3.705×10^{-09}
b_4	1.277×10^{-09}
b_5	3.588×10^{-11}
b_6	-3.146×10^{-15}
b_7	-3.553×10^{-13}
b_8	-4.292×10^{-14}

2.7.2 Scaling intensity to a constant elevation

One reason to correct counting rates to a constant elevation (or more precisely, mass shielding depth) is to have a common point of reference for N_0 comparisons. Another is so that the user can rescale N_0 to a different latitude using the sea level latitude curve. For these calculations one makes use of the exponential relation

$$f_{\text{bar}} = \exp[\bar{\beta}(x-x_0)] \quad (11)$$

where x is atmospheric depth over the counting interval, x_0 is a reference depth, assumed to be the sea level depth of 1033 g cm^{-2} and $\bar{\beta}$ is the *effective* atmospheric attenuation coefficient between x and x_0 at a given R_C . This is necessary because β changes with elevation, so it is more accurate to use an effective attenuation coefficient $\bar{\beta}$ between x and x_0 . This is given by

$$\bar{\beta} = n \left[1 + \exp(-\alpha R_C^{-k}) \right]^{-1} + \sum_{i=0}^q \frac{1}{(i+2)} (b_{3i} + b_{3i+1} R_C + b_{3i+2} R_C^2) x^{i+1} \Big|_{x_0}^x \quad (12)$$

where $q=3$ and the parameter values are given in Table 1. Note that this is just the integral of equation 10 over the depth range of interest.

2.8 Solar correction

The second factor corrects for variations in solar activity, and is calculated as

$$f_{\text{sol}} = 1 - \frac{M_0}{M(t)} (1 - \tau) \quad (13)$$

where $M(t)$ is the neutron intensity at time t , and M_0 is the counting rate at an arbitrarily chosen reference time and τ adjusts the ratio to the site of interest. At present, $M_0/M(t)$ is calculated on an hourly basis from the Jungfraujoch neutron monitor and reported at <https://crnslab.org>.

The variable τ was calculated from the global neutron monitor data set, using all sites with >30 months of data. The total number of sites meeting this criteria was 94. For each site in the network I normalized the intensity to 1 and then regressed the monthly average intensity at each site against the relative intensity at a reference site. The resulting slopes were fitted to the surface given by the equation below and in plotted in Figure 2. The reference site was originally chosen to be Climax, CO, USA which had been the longest continually serving neutron monitor in the world. Importantly, the Climax data set overlaps the peak period of neutron monitor observation which occurred surrounding the International Quiet Sun Year (1964-65). The Climax neutron monitor has since been decommissioned, but using our algorithm it is straightforward to adjust to any other reference station in the world.

The value of τ is well approximated by the following empirical relation:

$$\tau(x, R_C) = \varepsilon K(\ell_0 + \ell_1 x) [1 - \exp(-[\ell_2 + \ell_3 x] R_C^{\ell_4 + \ell_5 x})] \quad (12)$$

where K is a location-dependent normalization factor (discussed below) and ε is a correction factor that adjusts the sensitivity of the standard lead neutron monitor to that of rock, given as $\varepsilon = 1.14$ based on a comparison of latitude surveys with rock and lead neutrons monitors (i.e., rock neutron monitor is 14% more sensitive to solar modulations). Coefficients ℓ_i are provided in Table 2.

Figure 2. Values of τ and best fit surface.

Table 2. Parameters for calculating barometric pressure coefficient.

c_0	7.977×10^4
c_1	1.626×10^{-00}
c_2	3.990×10^{-03}
c_3	5.476×10^{-00}
c_4	-1.527×10^4
c_5	1.250×10^0

Our algorithm applies mainly to longer term fluctuations in neutron intensity, for which a straight correlation between monthly averages seems reasonable. Other methods will be required to accurately account for the effects of anomalous short term variations (e.g. Forbush events), as these tend to impact Earth unevenly (and in different ways) from event to event.

The value of K depends on the coordinates of the reference neutron monitor that is being used for the correction. It relates the sensitivity of the new reference neutron monitor (τ_{new}) to the sensitivity at Climax (τ_{cli}). Since τ_{cli} is defined to be 1, the correction is simply

$$K = \frac{1}{\tau_{\text{new}}} \quad (13)$$

For the Jungfraujoch neutron monitor ($x = 655 \text{ g cm}^{-2}$, $R_C = 4.5 \text{ GV}$), which has been used by the COSMOS network to correct for solar activity (Zreda et al., 2012), $K = 1.15$.

Humidity Correction

The third factor, f_{hum} , adjusts the counting rate for changes in the absolute humidity of the atmosphere (H). As absolute humidity rises the counting rate tends to drop. According to Rosolem et al. (2013), the neutron rate can be corrected with the formula

$$f_{\text{hum}} = 1 + 0.0054 \cdot H(t) \quad (14)$$

where $H(t)$ is in units of g m^{-3} . The absolute humidity of a well mixed atmosphere can be calculated from a local measurement of air temperature (T) and relative humidity (U) by first calculating the saturation vapour pressure,

$$e_w = 6.112 \exp\left(\frac{17.62T}{243.12 + T}\right) \quad (15)$$

where e_w is in hPa and T is in $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (WMO Guide, 2008), and then calculating absolute humidity as

$$H = \frac{U}{100} \left(\frac{e_w k}{T + 273.16} \right) \quad (16)$$

where U is expressed as a percentage and k is a constant equal to $216.68 \text{ g k J}^{-1}$ (Parish and Putnam, 1977).

Acknowledgments

References

- Carmichael, H., and Bercovitch, M., 1969, V. Analysis of IQSY cosmic-ray survey measurements. *Canadian Journal of Physics*, 47(19), 2073-2093.
- Desilets, D., Zreda, M. and Ferré, T.P.A., 2010, Nature's neutron probe: Land surface hydrology at an elusive scale with cosmic rays, *Water Resources Research* 46, W11505.
- Desilets, D., 2021, Cutoff rigidity calculations for cosmic ray neutron sensors, *Hydroinnova Technical Document* 21-01, doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5396587.
- Desorgher, L., 2004, Magnetocomics Soft-ware User Manual, *Physikalisches Institut University of Bern*, http://reat.space.qinetiq.com/septimes/magcos/magnetocomics_sum.pdf, Bern.
- Dorman, L. I., Fedchenko, S. G., Granitsky, L. V., and Rische, G. A., 1970, Coupling and barometer coefficients for measurements of cosmic ray variations at altitudes of 260-400 mb. In *International Cosmic Ray Conference* (Vol. 2, p. 233).
- Heiskanen, W. A. and Moritz, H. 1967, *Physical geodesy*. W.H. Freeman and Company, San Francisco.
- Hinze, W.J., Aiken, C., Brozena, J., Coakley, B., Dater, D., Flanagan, G., Forsberg, R., Hildenbrand, T., Keller, G.R., Kellogg, J. and Kucks, R., 2005, New standards for reducing gravity data: The North American gravity database. *Geophysics*, 70(4), pp.J25-J32.
- Moritz, H., 2000, Geodetic reference system 1980. *Journal of Geodesy*, 74(1), pp. 128-133.
- Parish, O.O. and Putnam, T.W., 1977, Equations for the determination of humidity from dew point from psychrometric data, *NASA Technical Note D-8401*, Dryden Flight Research Center, Edwards, CA.
- Rosolem, R., Shuttleworth, W.J., Zreda, M., Franz, T.E., Zeng, X. and Kurc, S.A., 2013, The effect of atmospheric water vapor on neutron count in the cosmic-ray soil moisture observing system. *Journal of Hydrometeorology*, 14(5), pp.1659-1671.
- Smart, D.F., Shea, M.A. and Flückiger, E.O., 2000, Magnetospheric models and trajectory computations. *Cosmic Rays and Earth*, pp.305-333.
- Villoresi, G., Dorman, L. I., Iucci, N., and Ptitsyna, N. G., 2000, Cosmic ray survey to Antarctica and coupling functions for neutron component near solar minimum (1996–1997): 1. Methodology and data quality assurance. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, 105(A9), 21025-21034.
- WMO Guide, 2008, Guide to Meteorological Instruments and Methods of Observation, Appendix 4B, *World Meteorological Organization*, WMO-No. 8 (CIMO Guide) Geneva.
- Zreda, M., Shuttleworth, W. J., Zeng, X., Zweck, C., Desilets, D., Franz, T., and Rosolem, R., 2012, COSMOS: The cosmic-ray soil moisture observing system. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, 16(11), 4079-4099.

Revision History